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Научная статья

**ЛИНГВОДИДАКТИЧЕСКИЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО
ТЕКСТА В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ КОММУНИКАТИВНОЙ
КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ УЧАЩИХСЯ СРЕДНЕЙ ШКОЛЫ**

**THE LINGUODIDACTIC POTENTIAL OF FICTION TEXT IN
DEVELOPING THE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF SECONDARY
SCHOOL STUDENTS**

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В статье рассматривается лингводидактический потенциал художественного текста как средства формирования коммуникативной компетенции учащихся средней школы. Особое внимание уделяется ключевым преимуществам применения художественных текстов на уроках иностранного языка в средней школе. Авторы подчеркивают, что грамотно подобранные художественные тексты становятся важным инструментом для формирования готовности учащихся к реальному речевому взаимодействию, соответствуя принципам системно-деятельностного подхода ФГОС. В ходе написания исследования были использованы такие методы как: изучение и анализ научной, научно-

методической и психолого-педагогической литературы по теме исследования, системный анализ учебно-методических материалов для создания целостной картины методологической базы формирования коммуникативной компетенции у школьников, сравнение.

This article examines the linguodidactic potential of fiction as a means of developing secondary school students' communicative competence. Particular attention is paid to the key advantages of using fiction in foreign language lessons in secondary schools. The authors emphasize that well-chosen fiction becomes an important tool for developing students' readiness for real-life verbal interaction, in line with the principles of the systemic-activity approach of the Federal State Educational Standard. The study utilized methods such as the study and analysis of scientific, methodological, and psychological-pedagogical literature on the topic, a systemic analysis of teaching and learning materials to create a comprehensive picture of the methodological basis for developing students' communicative competence, and comparison.

Ключевые слова: монологическая речь, диалогическая речь, художественная литература, иностранный язык, коммуникативная компетенция.

Key words: monologue speech, dialogic speech, fiction, foreign language, communicative competence.

Nowadays, foreign language proficiency is an important aspect of social and professional activity. Foreign language learning is aimed at developing communicative competence, which presupposes mastery of all types of speech activity. Speaking is the most essential skill, but perfecting it is the most difficult task and requires special attention from both the teacher and the student.

One of the most effective ways to develop oral communication skills is to use fiction texts in the learning process. Fiction has a unique ability to capture students' attention, expand their vocabulary, and develop creative thinking. Reading and discussing literary works not only deepens their understanding of the language but also introduces students to the cultural aspects of English-speaking countries. Furthermore, literary texts often contain lively, colloquial speech, which facilitates a more natural acquisition of linguistic structures and expressions. Thus, the relevance of our study stems from the fact that the use of fiction in English language teaching helps address several common methodological objectives simultaneously. Specifically, it develops and refines communication skills, helps establish emotional connections between students, teaches teamwork, unlocks students' creative potential, and increases motivation to learn a foreign language, even among low-performing students.

Fictional texts are works of literature created by authors to convey ideas, emotions, images, and plots through artistic expression. These include short stories, novels, poems, plays, and other forms of literary expression. Fictional texts are characterized by imagery, emotional intensity, and the use of a variety of linguistic devices, such as metaphors, epithets, similes, and idioms [1, p. 52–53].

Using fiction in teaching oral communication offers numerous practical advantages, making this approach not only effective but also engaging for students. Fiction serves as a powerful tool for developing language and communication skills, as well as for immersing students in the culture of the target language. Let us consider the key advantages of using fiction in foreign language lessons.

Fiction possesses unique linguistic potential, which helps enrich students' vocabulary and develop their linguistic intuition.

A variety of expressive devices—metaphors, epithets, idioms, and complex syntactic constructions—allow students to immerse themselves in the rich world of the English language. For example, descriptions of nature, emotions, or characters' actions provide students with ready-made models for constructing their own statements, which is especially important for developing oral and written communication skills.

Furthermore, the use of literary texts in foreign language teaching develops students' skills in working with context. Students begin to perceive the meaning of words and expressions not in isolation but within the context of a specific situation, which is essential for successful foreign language acquisition. This skill in working with context is especially important at the middle stage of learning, when texts become increasingly complex and students must interpret hidden meanings and subtexts.

In addition to their linguistic aspect, literary texts perform an important cultural function, reflecting traditions, values, historical events, and social realities. Familiarity with authentic literature immerses students in the cultural characteristics and mentality of native speakers of the target language, which is essential for developing intercultural competence.

Reading fiction stimulates cognitive and emotional development. Students engage in active thinking, including analyzing, interpreting, and critically evaluating the information they read. This teaches them to establish logical connections between elements of the content and formulate conclusions, which contributes to the development of cognitive abilities.

The emotional engagement that fiction evokes also plays an important role in the learning process. Learning becomes more engaging, and memorization is easier when it evokes emotion. For example, discussing characters' feelings or actions can become the basis for a lively and engaging dialogue in class [2, p. 296–297].

The potential for using fiction in English lessons is enormous. They can be used in tasks such as plot retelling, character descriptions, discussions on the topic of the reading, role-playing games, and creative thematic tasks [4, p. 78–80]. Creative tasks can be presented in the following form: coming up with a continuation of the story, creating dialogues between characters, or imagining oneself in the place of the characters. Such tasks not only develop language skills but also foster creativity and imagination.

An equally important advantage of using literary texts in teaching foreign language speaking is their ability to stimulate the development of communicative competence. Reading and discussing literary works create the conditions for the active use of language in oral form. Tasks involving retelling the plot, describing characters, discussing their actions and motives, and participating in role-playing games based on what has been read motivate the active use of foreign language speech, which, in turn, develops coherent speech in students and helps them construct their statements logically [5, p. 115–123].

The emotional expressiveness inherent in literary texts helps students master intonation, gestures, and other non-verbal communication tools. This is especially important for successful communication, as the emotional component plays a key role in interaction with the interlocutor [6, p. 115–123].

For example, as part of studying the topic "Science and Technology," students can be asked to read excerpts from the chapter "The Iron Man" (information about Iron Man's first appearance), followed by tasks to develop monologue and dialogic speech skills. For instance, to develop monologue speech, one can organize a creative task called "Gadget of the Future," in which students will take on the role of an inventor and present their product, or "The History of an Invention," in which students will talk about an existing invention, providing historical background. To develop dialogic speech skills, students can participate in a dialogue-discussion: "Robots Instead of Teachers?" or "Social Networks: Pros and Cons" (discussing the advantages and disadvantages of social networks, robots, etc.). As an additional task, one can offer "Interview with an Inventor," in which students role-play a dialogue where one student is the inventor of a product or the founder of a company, and the other is the interviewer.

In lessons on the topic of "Environmental Issues," students can be asked to read an excerpt from "The Lorax," which will be used to complete tasks such as "A Voice for Nature," which requires students to take on one of the suggested roles and prepare a statement using key phrases;

"Environmental Issues in My City," where students discuss the problems of their region; "Waste Sorting," where one student convinces another to sort their waste, and the latter challenges the arguments or requests additional information; and "Eco-Diary of an Endangered Species," which requires students to read an excerpt from "The Song of the Dodo," then choose a character to represent in a subsequent monologue, and then compose the monologue using the provided format.

However, the successful use of literary texts depends on their proper selection, which must adhere to certain principles. Therefore, it is crucial to examine each of them in order to understand what must be taken into account when choosing a literary text for teaching oral speech [8, p. 2870290].

1. Appropriateness to the students' age and interests. When choosing a literary text, it is necessary to consider the students' age characteristics and interests. Teenagers are more likely to be interested in topics related to their daily lives, hobbies, and current trends. Consequently, the choice falls on texts about sports, music, video games, social media, travel, the lives of teenagers in other countries, or fashion.

2. Accessibility of language. Literary texts should not only be accessible to students but also contain potential for language development. Grammatical and lexical material should be appropriate to the students' language proficiency level but also contain elements of novelty-lexical units, idioms, complex constructions, and set expressions.

At the initial stage, the teacher can use adapted literary texts that retain the key idea and plot but simplify their structure and language to ensure readability. As students' language skills improve, more complex texts are used, incorporating an increasing number of new words, idioms, grammatical and lexical structures, as well as cultural realities that students learn in context [7, p. 285–286].

3. Cultural Significance. Literary texts serve an important cultural function in the process of teaching foreign language speaking. They contain information about the culture, traditions, and realities of the country of the target language. It is this function of literary texts that introduces students to the peculiarities of life, history, and modern trends in other countries, broadening their horizons and helping to improve their language skills. For example, exposure to texts about national holidays, such as Thanksgiving in the United States or Halloween in the United Kingdom, helps students understand the traditions and values that are important to native speakers. Texts describing everyday life, whether school routines or family traditions, provide an opportunity to compare one's own culture with the culture of the country of the target language, identifying both differences and similarities.

4. Practical focus. The selected texts should be useful for developing speaking skills; that is, they should contain elements that can be used in oral speech. These may include dialogues, interviews, discussion situations, or discussion questions.

Dialogues presented in texts allow students to better master typical speech structures, intonations, and communication styles characteristic of native speakers of the target language.

Interviews introduce students to real speech, teach them how to ask questions, and maintain a conversation. Interviews with famous people or fictional characters can serve as a basis for expressing and arguing their opinions. Discussion situations encourage students to actively participate in dialogues where they must express their thoughts, agree or disagree with their interlocutor's point of view, and find compromises.

Finally, discussion questions included in the text help students develop argumentation and critical thinking skills. Students learn not only to express their opinions but also to listen to others, consider different points of view, and find common solutions.

5. Diversity of Genres. The use of texts of various genres in lessons is equally important: fiction, journalistic, scientific, and popular science. This helps develop children's communicative competence. For example, newspaper and magazine articles help develop reading skills and infor-

mation analysis; literary texts help develop an understanding of figurative language and emotional perception; and popular science materials help expand vocabulary and process facts.

6. Emotional intensity. Literary texts, above all, contain emotionally charged scenes. They can be used to develop skills in conveying emotions in oral speech. When working on a text, students describe the feelings of characters or their own emotions that arose while reading. This is an excellent opportunity to practice intonation, facial expressions, and gestures, which play a key role in oral communication. Reading dialogues filled with emotions allows students to experiment with intonation to convey joy, anger, or disappointment. Such activities not only improve pronunciation, making speech more natural and convincing, but also help teenagers understand the motives behind the actions of literary characters, which makes their speech more meaningful and reasoned.

7. Correspondence to educational goals. Fictional texts should be consistent with the educational goals and objectives of a specific lesson. For example, if the goal of the lesson is to develop descriptive skills, then texts with vivid descriptions of characters or natural settings should be used. If the goal is to develop argumentation skills, texts that address controversial topics and provoke discussion can be used [3, p. 11–13].

Fictional texts selected according to these criteria stimulate students not only to master new words and grammatical constructions but also to learn to express their thoughts, emotions, and opinions in a foreign language in a structured and well-reasoned manner. They also contribute to the development of critical thinking, creativity, and emotional intelligence, making the learning process deeper and more engaging.

In conclusion, it should be noted that developing oral communication skills requires not only systematic practice but also the use of authentic materials that can motivate students. Literary texts, possessing emotional and cultural value, create a natural context for communication, which aligns with the principles of the systemic-activity approach of the Federal State Educational Standard. This means they foster the development of universal learning activities and active learning and cognitive activity among students.

To ensure effective teaching using literary texts, the following criteria must be considered: a targeted selection of literary texts—linguistic complexity, cultural and linguistic relevance, topics that stimulate discussion, and sufficient volume for analysis and assignment completion; systematic development of speech skills, as well as linguodidactic support for the literary text, which includes linguistic supports in the form of vocabulary cards or speech clichés; multimedia materials; and differentiation of assignments by difficulty level.

Thus, properly organized work with literary texts in foreign language lessons in secondary school offers significant linguodidactic potential for developing students' ability and real readiness to communicate in accordance with goals, areas, and situations, as well as verbal interaction and mutual understanding. It also makes the learning process both effective and motivating.

СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

1. Воеводская Е.А., Медведев И.А. Художественный текст как средство достижения личностных результатов овладения иностранным языком // Проблемы современного педагогического образования. 2023. № 78 (3). С. 51–54.

2. Ерохина А.Б. Лингводидактический потенциал современной англоязычной малой прозы (для уровней b1-c1) // Филологические науки. Вопросы теории и практики. 2020. № 5. С. 295–301.

3. Журавлев А.П. Разработка критериев отбора текстов стихов и песен на английском языке для изучения лексики на среднем этапе обучения // Известия самарского научного центра российской академии наук. Социальные, гуманитарные, медико-биологические науки. 2020. Т. 22. № 73. С. 10–14.

4. Залавина Т.Ю., Гасаненко Е.А. Формирование коммуникативной компетенции как один из важных аспектов в обучении студентов иностранному языку // Проблемы современного педагогиче-

ского образования. 2021. № 70 (2). С. 78–81.

5. Оюн Д.О., Донгак Ч.Б. О роли чтения аутентичной литературы в обучении иностранному языку учащихся средних общеобразовательных школ г. Кызыла // Вестник Тувинского государственного университета. Педагогические науки. 2022. № 4 (103). С. 68–75.

6. Соловова Е.Н. Методика обучения иностранным языкам базовый курс: пособие для студентов педагогических вузов и учителей. Москва: АСТ, Астрель, 2008. 239 с.

7. Lineva E.A., Sadovskaya M.V., Sakharova A.V., Grushina M.V. Advantages and disadvantages of using internet resources in the educational process // На пересечении языков и культур. Актуальные вопросы гуманитарного знания. 2025. № 3 (33). С. 284–287.

8. Lineva E.A., Sadovskaya M.V., Sakharova A.V., Grushina M.V. Goals and objectives of developing speaking skills in secondary school // На пересечении языков и культур. Актуальные вопросы гуманитарного знания. 2025. № 3 (33). С. 287–291.

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